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Czech Republic**Title: SOP for Quantification of inflammatory proteins in serum/plasma using UHPLC/SRM-MS****Date: 14.4.2025****Version: version 3****Authors: Eliška Benešová, Veronika Vidová****Summary**

Inflammation is a defense response to stimulus, for example, infection, tissue damage, or cancer development, that the human body performs to attain homeostasis. The quantification of selected highly conserved APPs, such as C-reactive protein (CRP), α -1 antitrypsin (A1AT), serum amyloid A (SAA), and α -1-acid glycoprotein (A1AG), and other clinically relevant proteins including their isoforms, presumably allows for stratification among specific types of inflammation and for differentiation between physiological and pathological responses.

Table 1: Analyzed proteins and the targeted peptides

Accession number	Gene Name	Protein Name	Protein Acronym UniProt Entry Name	Target Peptide
P01876	IGHA1	Immunoglobulin heavy constant alpha 1	IGHA1	TPLTATLSK
P01009	SERPINA1	Alpha-1-antitrypsin	A1AT	FLENEDR LSITGTYDLK SVLGQLGITK
P01009-1	SERPINA1	Alpha-1-antitrypsin Isoform 1	A1AT-1	AVTIDEK FNKPFVFLMIEQNTK
PODJI8/PODJI9	SAA1/2	Serum amyloid A1 and A2	SAA1/2	SFFSFLGEAFDGAR EANYIGSDK
PODJI8	SAA1	Serum amyloid A1	SAA1	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR
PODJI9-1	SAA2	Serum amyloid A2 Isoform 1	SAA2-1	GAEDSLADQAANK LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK GPGGAWAAEVISNAR
P35542	SAA4	Serum amyloid A4	SAA4	FRPDGLPK EALQGVGDMGR GPGGVWAAK
P02741	CRP	C-reactive protein	CRP	ESDTSYVSLK
P02741-1	CRP	C-reactive protein isoform 1	CRP-1	GYSIFSATK
P02763	ORM1	Alpha-1-acid glycoprotein 1	A1AG1	NWGLSVYADKPETTK TYMLAFDVNDEK YVGGQEHFALLILR

P19652	ORM2	Alpha-1-acid glycoprotein 2	A1AG2	SDVMYTDWK TLMFGSYLDDEK EHVAHLLFLR
P02763/ P19652	ORM1/2	Alpha-1-acid glycoprotein 1 and 2	A1AG1/2	WFYIASAFR
P10645	CHGA	Chromogranin-A	CHGA	ELQDLALQGAK VAHQQLALR
P02649	APOE	Apolipoprotein E	APOE	LGPLVEQGR
P78423	CX3CL1	Fractalkine	CX3CL1	AQDGGPVGTELFR
P08697-1	SERPINF2	Alpha-2-antiplasmin isoform 1	SERPINF2-1	LGNQEPGGQTALK
P08697	SERPINF2	Alpha-2-antiplasmin	SERPINF2	FDPSLTQR DFLQSLK
P02647	APOA1	Apolipoprotein A-I	APOA1	DYVSQFEGSALGK AKPALEDLR
P01857	IGHG1	Immunoglobulin heavy constant gamma 1	IGHG1	TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSK GPSVFPLAPSSK
P01859	IGHG2	Immunoglobulin heavy constant gamma 2	IGHG2	GLPAPIEK
P01860	IGHG3	Immunoglobulin heavy constant gamma 3	IGHG3	TPLGDTTHTCPR SCDTPPPCPR
P01861	IGHG4	Immunoglobulin heavy constant gamma 4	IGHG4	TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSR GLPSSIEK
P01857/ P01859/ P01860/ P01831	IGHG1/2/3/4	Immunoglobulin heavy constant gamma 1/2/3/4	IGHG1/2/3/4	DTLMISR NQVSLTCLVK
P00738	HP	Haptoglobin	HP	TEGDGVYTLNNEK VGYVSGWGR
P01023	A2M	Alpha-2-macroglobulin	A2M	AIGYLNTGYQR NEDSLVVFQTDK
P05109	S100-A8	Calprotectin 1	CAL1	ALNSIIDVYHK GADVWFK
P06702	S100-A9	Calprotectin 2	CAL2	LGHPTLNQGEFK DLQNFLK
P05164	MPO	Myeloperoxidase	MPO	IANVFTNAFR QNQIADVDEIR VVLEGGIDPILR
P01034	CST3	Cystatin-C	CST3	ALDFAVGEYNK
P01042	KNG1	Kininogen-1	KNG1	YFIDFVAR QVVAGLNFR TVGSDTFYFSK
P18428	LBP	Lipopolysaccharide-binding protein	LBP	ITLPDFTGDLR LAEGFPLPLLK
P02760	AMBP	Protein AMBP	AMBP	GVCEETSGAYEK ETLLQDFR
P61769	B2M	Beta-2-microglobulin	B2M	VNHVTLQSQPK

Safety information

- Serum/plasma samples are classified as biohazardous material & thus all items in contact (e.g. pipette tips, vials) should be disposed of appropriately.

Overview of reagents

- ammonium bicarbonate buffer (ABB), RapiGest, dithiothreitol (DTT), iodoacetamide (IAA), trypsin gold, acetic acid, acetonitrile (ACN) LC-MS grade, formic acid (FA) LC-MS grade, miliQ water

Equipment

- 10 μ L, 200 μ L, and 1000 μ L pipette
- 10 μ L, 100 μ L, and 300 μ L multichannel pipette
- 1200 μ L automatic multichannel pipette
- Orbital shaker incubator
- Centrifugal evaporator
- Mini vortex or vortex for 96-well plates
- Centrifuge with rotor for 96-well plates
- pH meter
- 96-well plates
- SPE manifold with pump

LC-MS equipment

- Vanquish Neo UHPLC coupled with TSQ Altis Plus
- Easy-Spray Pep Map column (RSLC C18, 2 μ m, 15cmX150 μ m, ES906)

Consumables & glassware

- 50 mL Falcon screw cap plastic vials
- 700 μ L 96-well plates with silicone sealing
- 10 μ L, 100 μ L, 200 μ L, 300 μ L, 1000 μ L, and 1200 μ L tips
- 500 μ L Eppendorf tubes
- 250 μ L Polypropylen vials with screw lid
- 96 well plate SPE HLB PRIME 30 mg

Reagents for standard and sample preparation

Protein extraction buffer

- 50 mM ABB: dissolve 40 mg ABB in 10 mL of MiliQ water
- Solution should have pH=7.8 (measure with pH meter)
- 1 mg/mL RapiGest: dissolve 1 mg of RapiGest in 1 mL of 50 mM ABB
- 0.1 mg/mL RapiGest buffer: mix 100 μ L of 1 mg/mL RapiGest with 900 μ L of ABB

Reduction and alkylation solutions

- 200 mM DTT: dissolve 30.8 mg in 1 mL of miliQ water
- 400 mM IAA: dissolve 74 mg in 1 mL of miliQ water

Trypsin solution

- As described in trypsin standard manual, dissolve 100 μ g lyophilized trypsin in 100 μ L of 50 mM acetic acid.

SPE solutions

- 2% FA (pH<3)
- 0.1% FA
- 50% ACN with 0.1%FA
- 5% ACN with 0.1% FA

Reagents for mobile phase preparation

- ACN in LC-MS grade, FA in LC-MS grade, milliQ water

Standard preparation

- To prepare 1 mL of SIL mixture, pipette defined volume of 10 μ M peptide 3w3 standard listed in **Table 2** and 533 μ L of 20% ACN with 0.1 mg/mL RapiGest buffer.

Table 2: SIL mixture volumes and concentrations

Protein acronym	Peptide sequence	Peptide concentration in 3w3 SIL mixture [nM]	Volume of 10 μ M standard [μ L]	Peptide concentration in sample [40 μ L]
IGHA1	TPLTATLSK	100	10	25
A1AT	FLENEDR	100	10	25
	LSITGTYDLK	200	20	50
	SVLGQLGITK	200	20	50
A1AT1-1	AVLTIDEK	160	16	40
	FNKPFVFLMIEQNTK	200	20	50
SAA1/2	SFFSFLGEAFDGAR	20	2	5
	EANYIGSDK	20	2	5
SAA1	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR	20	2	5
SAA2-1	GPGGAWAAEVISNAR	20	2	5
	GAEDSLADQAANK	20	2	5
	LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK	20	2	5
SAA4	EALQGVGDMGR	40	4	10
	FRPDGLPK	20	2	5
	GPGGVWAAK	20	2	5
CRP	ESDTSYVSLK	20	2	5
CRP-1	GYSIFSATK	20	2	5
A1AG1	NWGLSVYADKPETTK	80	8	20
	TYMLAFDVNDEK	60	6	15
	YVGGQEHFAHLLILR	60	6	15
A1AG2	SDVMYTDWK	40	4	10
	TLMFGSYLDDEK	20	2	5
	EHVAHLLFLR	60	6	15
A1AG1/2	WFYIASAFR	120	12	30
CHGA	ELQDLALQGAK	20	2	5
	VAHQQLALR	20	2	5
APOE	LGPLVEQGR	20	2	5
CX3CL1	AQDGGPVGTELFR	20	2	5
SerpinF2 Iso 1	LGNQEPGGQTALK	20	2	5
SerpinF2	FDPSLTQR	20	2	5
	DFLQSLK	20	2	5
APOA1	DYVSQFEQSALGK	160	16	40
	AKPALEDLR	160	16	40

IGHG1	TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSK	300	30	75
	GPSVFPLAPSSK	300	30	75
IGHG2	GLPAPIEK	200	20	50
IGHG3	TPLGDTTHTCPR	25	2.5	6.25
	SCDTPPPCPR	25	2.5	6.25
IGHG4	TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSR	20	2	5
	GLPSSIEK	20	2	5
IGHG1/2/3/4	DTLMISR	500	50	125
	NQVSLTCLVK	500	50	125
HP	TEGDGVYTLNNEK	120	12	30
	VGYVSGWGR	120	12	30
A2M	AIGYLNTGYQR	20	2	5
	NEDSLVQVQTDK	20	2	5
CAL1	ALNSIIDVYHK	20	2	5
	GADVWFK	20	2	5
CAL2	LGHPDTLNQGEFK	20	2	5
	DLQNFLK	20	2	5
MPO	IANVFTNAFR	20	2	5
	QNQIAVDEIR	20	2	5
	VVLEGGIDPILR	20	2	5
CST3	ALDFAVGEYNK	20	2	5
KNG1	YFIDFVAR	20	2	5
	QVVAGLNFR	100	10	25
	TVGSDTFYSFK	20	2	5
LBP	ITLPDFTGDLR	20	2	5
	LAEGFPLPLLK	20	2	5
AMBP	GVCEETSGAYEK	20	2	5
	ETLLQDFR	20	2	5
B2M	VNHVTLSQPK	20	2	5

Protein extraction

1. Take serum/plasma samples from -80 °C freezer and leave thaw on ice for 60 min.
2. Pipette a 2 µL into a 500 µL tube and add 98 µL of 0.1 mg/mL RapiGest buffer.
3. Place onto the shaker and shake 1200 RPM for 10 min at room temperature.
4. Dilute extract 10x (e.g. take 10 µL of extract and add 90 µL of 0.1 mg/mL RapiGest buffer) and shake 1200 RPM for 10 min at room temperature.
5. Take a 10 µL of diluted extract for total protein analysis using BCA kit.
6. Take 20 µL of diluted extract for target protein analysis and place into a 700 µL deep well plate.

Reduction and alkylation

7. Add 1 μL of DTT solution and incubate at 90 °C for 10 min in heated block.
8. Leave to cool down for 10 minutes.
9. Add 1 μL of IAA solution and incubate in dark for 30 min at room temperature.

Trypsin digestion

10. Add 10 μL of SIL 3w3 mixture to the sample.
11. Dilute the trypsin solution 5x using 50 mM acetic acid to final concentration 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$.
12. Add 2 μL of diluted trypsin solution to the sample.
13. Seal microplate with silicone seal.
14. Place into a heat shaker and shake at 200 RPM for 17 hours at 37 °C.
15. Stop digestion adding 200 μL of 2% FA.

SPE in 96-well microplate format

16. Load sample solution into a SPE well and turn vacuum on to elute solution into waste.
17. Wash sample with 300 μL of 0.1% FA.
18. Elute peptides with 200 μL of 50% ACN with 0.1% FA into a 700 μL microplate with V bottom.
19. Dry out the sample in centrifugal evaporator at 40 °C for 3h.
20. Store in freezer -20 °C or dissolve samples for UHPLC/MS analysis.
21. Dissolve in 40 μL of 5% ACN with 0.1% FA.
22. Vortex properly.
23. Centrifuge sample for 5 min at 4000 rpm.
24. Analyze using UHPLC/MS.

Mobile phase and wash preparation

- Mobile phase A: 0.1% FA
- Mobile phase B: 100% ACN with 0.1% FA

- Strong wash: 80% ACN with 0.1% FA
- Weak wash: 0.1% FA
- Seal wash: 75% IPA with 0.1% FA

Vanquish NEO – TSQ Altis Plus analysis

25. Prepare Vanquish NEO – TSQ Altis Plus according to the *SOP for Preparation of Vanquish Neo UHPLC-TSQ Altis Plus for analysis*.
26. Use dSRM assay as shown in **Table 3** with Vanquish NEO – TSQ Altis Plus method setup shown in **Table 4**.
27. Inject 3 μ L of samples to the UHPLC Vanquish NEO equipped with Easy-Spray Pep Map column (RSLC C18, 2 μ m, 15cmX150 μ m, ES906) thermostated at 40 $^{\circ}$ C.
28. Start LC-MS analysis sequence.
29. Check initial blanks and QC.
30. Store samples at -20 $^{\circ}$ C.

NOTE: If there are problems, stop sequence, cap/seal samples and store at -20 $^{\circ}$ C whilst troubleshooting.

Table 3. dSRM assay in analytical method

Compound	Retention Time (min)	RT Window (min)	Precursor (m/z)	Product (m/z)	Collision Energy (V)
VNHVTL SQPK	3.6	2	374.88	459.256	8.7
VNHVTL SQPK	3.6	2	374.88	512.283	8.7
VNHVTL SQPK	3.6	2	374.88	572.34	8.7
VNHVTL SQPK	3.6	2	377.551	467.27	8.7
VNHVTL SQPK	3.6	2	377.551	516.29	8.7
VNHVTL SQPK	3.6	2	377.551	580.354	8.7
SCDTPPPCPR	3.6	2	593.753	362.184	20.7
SCDTPPPCPR	3.6	2	593.753	626.308	20.7
SCDTPPPCPR	3.6	2	593.753	723.361	20.7
SCDTPPPCPR	3.6	2	598.757	367.188	20.7
SCDTPPPCPR	3.6	2	598.757	636.316	20.7
SCDTPPPCPR	3.6	2	598.757	733.369	20.7
TPLGDTTHTCPR	3.7	2	678.322	771.357	23.3
TPLGDTTHTCPR	3.7	2	678.322	1044.453	23.3

TPLGDTTHTCPR	3.7	2	678.322	1157.537	23.3
TPLGDTTHTCPR	3.7	2	683.326	781.365	23.3
TPLGDTTHTCPR	3.7	2	683.326	1054.461	23.3
TPLGDTTHTCPR	3.7	2	683.326	1167.545	23.3
VAHQLQALR	4.1	2	345.873	359.24	15.4
VAHQLQALR	4.1	2	345.873	468.772	15.4
VAHQLQALR	4.1	2	345.873	487.299	15.4
VAHQLQALR	4.1	2	349.21	369.248	15.4
VAHQLQALR	4.1	2	349.21	473.776	15.4
VAHQLQALR	4.1	2	349.21	497.307	15.4
EANYIGSDK	4.2	2	498.735	406.193	17.9
EANYIGSDK	4.2	2	498.735	519.277	17.9
EANYIGSDK	4.2	2	498.735	682.341	17.9
EANYIGSDK	4.2	2	502.742	414.207	17.9
EANYIGSDK	4.2	2	502.742	527.292	17.9
EANYIGSDK	4.2	2	502.742	690.355	17.9
GVCEETSGAYEK	4.2	2	665.29	755.36	26.2
GVCEETSGAYEK	4.2	2	665.29	884.4	26.2
GVCEETSGAYEK	4.2	2	665.29	1013.44	26.2
GVCEETSGAYEK	4.2	2	669.29	763.37	26.2
GVCEETSGAYEK	4.2	2	669.29	892.41	26.2
GVCEETSGAYEK	4.2	2	669.29	1021.46	26.2
LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK	4.5	2	566.608	531.289	23.8
LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK	4.5	2	566.608	646.315	23.8
LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK	4.5	2	566.608	717.353	23.8
LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK	4.5	2	569.279	539.303	23.8
LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK	4.5	2	569.279	654.33	23.8
LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK	4.5	2	569.279	725.367	23.8
LGNQEPGGQTALK	4.6	2	656.846	542.257	22.6
LGNQEPGGQTALK	4.6	2	656.846	771.436	22.6
LGNQEPGGQTALK	4.6	2	656.846	900.479	22.6
LGNQEPGGQTALK	4.6	2	660.854	542.257	22.6
LGNQEPGGQTALK	4.6	2	660.854	779.45	22.6
LGNQEPGGQTALK	4.6	2	660.854	908.493	22.6
FRPDGLPK	4.8	2	310.512	244.166	14.1
FRPDGLPK	4.8	2	310.512	313.679	14.1
FRPDGLPK	4.8	2	310.512	573.278	14.1
FRPDGLPK	4.8	2	313.183	252.18	14.1
FRPDGLPK	4.8	2	313.183	317.686	14.1
FRPDGLPK	4.8	2	313.183	573.278	14.1
FLENEDR	4.8	2	461.72	533.23	20.2

FLENEDR	4.8	2	461.72	662.27	20.2
FLENEDR	4.8	2	461.72	775.36	20.2
FLENEDR	4.8	2	466.72	543.24	20.2
FLENEDR	4.8	2	466.72	672.28	20.2
FLENEDR	4.8	2	466.72	785.37	20.2
AKPAEDLR	5.0	2	338.198	288.203	15.1
AKPAEDLR	5.0	2	338.198	403.23	15.1
AKPAEDLR	5.0	2	338.198	532.273	15.1
AKPAEDLR	5.0	2	341.534	298.211	15.1
AKPAEDLR	5.0	2	341.534	413.238	15.1
AKPAEDLR	5.0	2	341.534	542.281	15.1
GAEDSLADQAANK	5.0	2	645.302	646.315	22.3
GAEDSLADQAANK	5.0	2	645.302	717.353	22.3
GAEDSLADQAANK	5.0	2	645.302	1032.496	22.3
GAEDSLADQAANK	5.0	2	649.309	654.33	22.3
GAEDSLADQAANK	5.0	2	649.309	725.367	22.3
GAEDSLADQAANK	5.0	2	649.309	1040.51	22.3
GLPSSIEK	5.1	2	415.735	330.682	15.4
GLPSSIEK	5.1	2	415.735	563.304	15.4
GLPSSIEK	5.1	2	415.735	660.356	15.4
GLPSSIEK	5.1	2	419.742	334.689	15.4
GLPSSIEK	5.1	2	419.742	571.318	15.4
GLPSSIEK	5.1	2	419.742	668.37	15.4
GPGGVWAAK	5.1	2	421.73	289.19	19.1
GPGGVWAAK	5.1	2	421.73	475.27	19.1
GPGGVWAAK	5.1	2	421.73	688.38	19.1
GPGGVWAAK	5.1	2	425.74	297.2	19.1
GPGGVWAAK	5.1	2	425.74	483.28	19.1
GPGGVWAAK	5.1	2	425.74	696.39	19.1
LGHPDTLNQGEFK	5.4	2	485.912	480.245	20.7
LGHPDTLNQGEFK	5.4	2	485.912	621.299	20.7
LGHPDTLNQGEFK	5.4	2	485.912	722.347	20.7
LGHPDTLNQGEFK	5.4	2	488.583	488.259	20.7
LGHPDTLNQGEFK	5.4	2	488.583	621.299	20.7
LGHPDTLNQGEFK	5.4	2	488.583	730.361	20.7
EALQGVGDMGR	6.4	2	566.774	201.087	19.9
EALQGVGDMGR	6.4	2	566.774	535.229	19.9
EALQGVGDMGR	6.4	2	566.774	691.319	19.9
EALQGVGDMGR	6.4	2	571.779	201.087	19.9
EALQGVGDMGR	6.4	2	571.779	545.238	19.9
EALQGVGDMGR	6.4	2	571.779	701.327	19.9

GLPAPIEK	5.7	2	412.747	327.695	15.3
GLPAPIEK	5.7	2	412.747	486.292	15.3
GLPAPIEK	5.7	2	412.747	654.382	15.3
GLPAPIEK	5.7	2	416.755	331.702	15.3
GLPAPIEK	5.7	2	416.755	494.306	15.3
GLPAPIEK	5.7	2	416.755	662.396	15.3
AVLTIDEK	6.0	2	444.755	171.113	16.2
AVLTIDEK	6.0	2	444.755	605.314	16.2
AVLTIDEK	6.0	2	444.755	718.398	16.2
AVLTIDEK	6.0	2	448.763	171.113	16.2
AVLTIDEK	6.0	2	448.763	613.328	16.2
AVLTIDEK	6.0	2	448.763	726.412	16.2
TPLTATLSK	6.0	2	466.277	415.753	16.9
TPLTATLSK	6.0	2	466.277	519.314	16.9
TPLTATLSK	6.0	2	466.277	733.445	16.9
TPLTATLSK	6.0	2	470.284	419.76	16.9
TPLTATLSK	6.0	2	470.284	527.328	16.9
TPLTATLSK	6.0	2	470.284	741.46	16.9
FDPSLTQR	6.0	2	482.248	351.201	17.4
FDPSLTQR	6.0	2	482.248	604.341	17.4
FDPSLTQR	6.0	2	482.248	701.394	17.4
FDPSLTQR	6.0	2	487.252	356.205	17.4
FDPSLTQR	6.0	2	487.252	614.35	17.4
FDPSLTQR	6.0	2	487.252	711.402	17.4
LGPLVEQGR	6.0	2	484.78	360.199	17.4
LGPLVEQGR	6.0	2	484.78	489.242	17.4
LGPLVEQGR	6.0	2	484.78	588.31	17.4
LGPLVEQGR	6.0	2	489.784	370.207	17.4
LGPLVEQGR	6.0	2	489.784	499.25	17.4
LGPLVEQGR	6.0	2	489.784	598.318	17.4
TEGDVYTLNNEK	6.0	2	720.336	231.098	24.5
TEGDVYTLNNEK	6.0	2	720.336	718.373	24.5
TEGDVYTLNNEK	6.0	2	720.336	881.436	24.5
TEGDVYTLNNEK	6.0	2	724.343	231.098	24.5
TEGDVYTLNNEK	6.0	2	724.343	726.387	24.5
TEGDVYTLNNEK	6.0	2	724.343	889.451	24.5
ESDTSYVSLK	6.1	2	564.775	347.229	19.8
ESDTSYVSLK	6.1	2	564.775	609.361	19.8
ESDTSYVSLK	6.1	2	564.775	696.393	19.8
ESDTSYVSLK	6.1	2	568.782	355.243	19.8
ESDTSYVSLK	6.1	2	568.782	617.375	19.8

ESDTSYVSLK	6.1	2	568.782	704.407	19.8
QNQIAVDEIR	6.3	2	593.314	532.273	20.7
QNQIAVDEIR	6.3	2	593.314	631.341	20.7
QNQIAVDEIR	6.3	2	593.314	702.378	20.7
QNQIAVDEIR	6.3	2	598.318	542.281	20.7
QNQIAVDEIR	6.3	2	598.318	641.349	20.7
QNQIAVDEIR	6.3	2	598.318	712.386	20.7
DTLMISR	6.5	2	418.221	375.235	15.5
DTLMISR	6.5	2	418.221	506.276	15.5
DTLMISR	6.5	2	418.221	619.36	15.5
DTLMISR	6.5	2	423.225	385.243	15.5
DTLMISR	6.5	2	423.225	516.284	15.5
DTLMISR	6.5	2	423.225	629.368	15.5
GADVWFK	7.0	2	411.71	480.261	15.3
GADVWFK	7.0	2	411.71	579.329	15.3
GADVWFK	7.0	2	411.71	694.356	15.3
GADVWFK	7.0	2	415.717	488.275	15.3
GADVWFK	7.0	2	415.717	587.343	15.3
GADVWFK	7.0	2	415.717	702.37	15.3
AIGYLNTGYQR	7.0	2	628.325	738.353	25.1
AIGYLNTGYQR	7.0	2	628.325	851.437	25.1
AIGYLNTGYQR	7.0	2	628.325	1071.522	25.1
AIGYLNTGYQR	7.0	2	633.329	748.361	25.1
AIGYLNTGYQR	7.0	2	633.329	861.445	25.1
AIGYLNTGYQR	7.0	2	633.329	1081.53	25.1
EHVAHLLFLR	7.1	2	412.24	435.27	10.0
EHVAHLLFLR	7.1	2	412.24	484.81	10.0
EHVAHLLFLR	7.1	2	412.24	548.36	10.0
EHVAHLLFLR	7.1	2	415.58	440.28	10.0
EHVAHLLFLR	7.1	2	415.58	489.81	10.0
EHVAHLLFLR	7.1	2	415.58	558.36	10.0
VGYSVGWGR	7.2	2	490.751	320.16	17.6
VGYSVGWGR	7.2	2	490.751	562.273	17.6
VGYSVGWGR	7.2	2	490.751	661.342	17.6
VGYSVGWGR	7.2	2	495.755	320.16	17.6
VGYSVGWGR	7.2	2	495.755	572.281	17.6
VGYSVGWGR	7.2	2	495.755	671.35	17.6
QVAGLNFR	7.5	1.8	502.29	606.34	21.4
QVAGLNFR	7.5	1.8	502.29	677.37	21.4
QVAGLNFR	7.5	1.8	502.29	776.44	21.4
QVAGLNFR	7.5	1.8	507.291	616.344	21.4

QVVAGLNFR	7.5	1.8	507.291	687.381	21.4
QVVAGLNFR	7.5	1.8	507.291	786.449	21.4
NWGLSVYADKPETTK	7.5	1.8	570.29	301.13	24.0
NWGLSVYADKPETTK	7.5	1.8	570.29	526.767	24.0
NWGLSVYADKPETTK	7.5	1.8	570.29	704.87	24.0
NWGLSVYADKPETTK	7.5	1.8	572.961	301.13	24.0
NWGLSVYADKPETTK	7.5	1.8	572.961	530.774	24.0
NWGLSVYADKPETTK	7.5	1.8	572.961	708.877	24.0
ALNSIIDVYHK	7.5	1.8	636.85	284.172	22.0
ALNSIIDVYHK	7.5	1.8	636.85	661.33	22.0
ALNSIIDVYHK	7.5	1.8	636.85	774.414	22.0
ALNSIIDVYHK	7.5	1.8	640.858	292.186	22.0
ALNSIIDVYHK	7.5	1.8	640.858	669.345	22.0
ALNSIIDVYHK	7.5	1.8	640.858	782.429	22.0
YVGGQEHFAHLLILR	7.7	1.8	438.99	263.14	11.0
YVGGQEHFAHLLILR	7.7	1.8	438.99	497.61	11.0
YVGGQEHFAHLLILR	7.7	1.8	438.99	530.64	11.0
YVGGQEHFAHLLILR	7.7	1.8	441.5	263.14	11.0
YVGGQEHFAHLLILR	7.7	1.8	441.5	500.95	11.0
YVGGQEHFAHLLILR	7.7	1.8	441.5	533.97	11.0
ELQDLALQGAK	7.8	1.8	593.327	516.314	20.7
ELQDLALQGAK	7.8	1.8	593.327	587.351	20.7
ELQDLALQGAK	7.8	1.8	593.327	815.462	20.7
ELQDLALQGAK	7.8	1.8	597.334	524.328	20.7
ELQDLALQGAK	7.8	1.8	597.334	595.365	20.7
ELQDLALQGAK	7.8	1.8	597.334	823.476	20.7
NQVSLTCLVK	7.9	1.8	581.318	243.109	20.3
NQVSLTCLVK	7.9	1.8	581.318	820.46	20.3
NQVSLTCLVK	7.9	1.8	581.318	919.528	20.3
NQVSLTCLVK	7.9	1.8	585.326	243.109	20.3
NQVSLTCLVK	7.9	1.8	585.326	828.474	20.3
NQVSLTCLVK	7.9	1.8	585.326	927.542	20.3
TVGSDFYSFK	7.9	1.8	626.3	201.12	25.1
TVGSDFYSFK	7.9	1.8	626.3	381.21	25.1
TVGSDFYSFK	7.9	1.8	626.3	1051.47	25.1
TVGSDFYSFK	7.9	1.8	630.305	201.123	25.1
TVGSDFYSFK	7.9	1.8	630.305	389.227	25.1
TVGSDFYSFK	7.9	1.8	630.305	1059.487	25.1
NEDSLVQVQTDK	7.9	1.8	697.843	590.314	27.2
NEDSLVQVQTDK	7.9	1.8	697.843	737.383	27.2
NEDSLVQVQTDK	7.9	1.8	697.843	1151.594	27.2

NEDSLVQTDK	7.9	1.8	701.85	598.329	27.2
NEDSLVQTDK	7.9	1.8	701.85	745.397	27.2
NEDSLVQTDK	7.9	1.8	701.85	1159.608	27.2
LSITGYDLK	8.0	1.8	555.81	696.36	23.0
LSITGYDLK	8.0	1.8	555.81	797.4	23.0
LSITGYDLK	8.0	1.8	555.81	910.49	23.0
LSITGYDLK	8.0	1.8	559.81	704.37	23.0
LSITGYDLK	8.0	1.8	559.81	805.42	23.0
LSITGYDLK	8.0	1.8	559.81	918.5	23.0
SDVMYTDWK	8.0	1.8	572.753	302.135	20.1
SDVMYTDWK	8.0	1.8	572.753	712.33	20.1
SDVMYTDWK	8.0	1.8	572.753	843.371	20.1
SDVMYTDWK	8.0	1.8	576.76	302.135	20.1
SDVMYTDWK	8.0	1.8	576.76	720.344	20.1
SDVMYTDWK	8.0	1.8	576.76	851.385	20.1
IANVFTNAFR	8.0	1.8	576.812	299.171	18.9
IANVFTNAFR	8.0	1.8	576.812	608.315	18.9
IANVFTNAFR	8.0	1.8	576.812	755.383	18.9
IANVFTNAFR	8.0	1.8	581.816	299.171	18.9
IANVFTNAFR	8.0	1.8	581.816	618.323	18.9
IANVFTNAFR	8.0	1.8	581.816	765.392	18.9
ALDFAVGEYNK	8.0	1.8	613.81	610.28	24.7
ALDFAVGEYNK	8.0	1.8	613.81	709.35	24.7
ALDFAVGEYNK	8.0	1.8	613.81	780.39	24.7
ALDFAVGEYNK	8.0	1.8	617.81	618.3	24.7
ALDFAVGEYNK	8.0	1.8	617.81	717.37	24.7
ALDFAVGEYNK	8.0	1.8	617.81	788.4	24.7
VVLEGGIDPILR	8.0	1.8	640.882	312.228	22.1
VVLEGGIDPILR	8.0	1.8	640.882	498.34	22.1
VVLEGGIDPILR	8.0	1.8	640.882	840.494	22.1
VVLEGGIDPILR	8.0	1.8	645.886	312.228	22.1
VVLEGGIDPILR	8.0	1.8	645.886	508.348	22.1
VVLEGGIDPILR	8.0	1.8	645.886	850.502	22.1
GPSVFPLAPSSK	8.1	1.8	593.827	418.23	20.7
GPSVFPLAPSSK	8.1	1.8	593.827	699.404	20.7
GPSVFPLAPSSK	8.1	1.8	593.827	846.472	20.7
GPSVFPLAPSSK	8.1	1.8	597.834	426.244	20.7
GPSVFPLAPSSK	8.1	1.8	597.834	707.418	20.7
GPSVFPLAPSSK	8.1	1.8	597.834	854.486	20.7
AQDGGPVGTELF	8.1	1.8	673.839	200.103	23.1
AQDGGPVGTELF	8.1	1.8	673.839	722.383	23.1

AQDGGPVGTELFR	8.1	1.8	673.839	1147.574	23.1
AQDGGPVGTELFR	8.1	1.8	678.843	200.103	23.1
AQDGGPVGTELFR	8.1	1.8	678.843	732.391	23.1
AQDGGPVGTELFR	8.1	1.8	678.843	1157.582	23.1
SVLGQLGITK	8.1	1.8	1015.62	248.16	36.5
SVLGQLGITK	8.1	1.8	1015.62	418.27	36.5
SVLGQLGITK	8.1	1.8	1015.62	531.35	36.5
SVLGQLGITK	8.1	1.8	1023.63	256.18	36.5
SVLGQLGITK	8.1	1.8	1023.63	426.28	36.5
SVLGQLGITK	8.1	1.8	1023.63	539.36	36.5
DLQNFLK	8.2	1.8	439.242	260.197	16.1
DLQNFLK	8.2	1.8	439.242	521.308	16.1
DLQNFLK	8.2	1.8	439.242	649.367	16.1
DLQNFLK	8.2	1.8	443.249	268.211	16.1
DLQNFLK	8.2	1.8	443.249	529.322	16.1
DLQNFLK	8.2	1.8	443.249	657.381	16.1
ETLLQDFR	8.2	1.8	511.27	322.19	21.7
ETLLQDFR	8.2	1.8	511.27	565.27	21.7
ETLLQDFR	8.2	1.8	511.27	678.36	21.7
ETLLQDFR	8.2	1.8	516.27	332.2	21.7
ETLLQDFR	8.2	1.8	516.27	575.28	21.7
ETLLQDFR	8.2	1.8	516.27	688.37	21.7
GYSIFSATK	8.2	1.8	568.79	248.16	23.4
GYSIFSATK	8.2	1.8	568.79	716.36	23.4
GYSIFSATK	8.2	1.8	568.79	916.48	23.4
GYSIFSATK	8.2	1.8	572.791	256.174	23.4
GYSIFSATK	8.2	1.8	572.791	724.375	23.4
GYSIFSATK	8.2	1.8	572.791	924.491	23.4
FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR	8.2	1.8	726.659	661.305	29.9
FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR	8.2	1.8	726.659	732.342	29.9
FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR	8.2	1.8	726.659	803.379	29.9
FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR	8.2	1.8	729.995	671.314	29.9
FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR	8.2	1.8	729.995	742.351	29.9
FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR	8.2	1.8	729.995	813.388	29.9
DFLQSLK	8.3	1.8	425.737	263.103	15.7
DFLQSLK	8.3	1.8	425.737	475.287	15.7
DFLQSLK	8.3	1.8	425.737	588.372	15.7
DFLQSLK	8.3	1.8	429.744	263.103	15.7
DFLQSLK	8.3	1.8	429.744	483.302	15.7
DFLQSLK	8.3	1.8	429.744	596.386	15.7
GPGGAWAAEVISNAR	8.3	1.8	728.371	340.162	24.8

GPGGAWAAEVISNAR	8.3	1.8	728.371	859.463	24.8
GPGGAWAAEVISNAR	8.3	1.8	728.371	930.5	24.8
GPGGAWAAEVISNAR	8.3	1.8	733.375	340.162	24.8
GPGGAWAAEVISNAR	8.3	1.8	733.375	869.471	24.8
GPGGAWAAEVISNAR	8.3	1.8	733.375	940.509	24.8
YFIDFVAR	8.4	1.8	515.77	492.29	21.8
YFIDFVAR	8.4	1.8	515.77	607.32	21.8
YFIDFVAR	8.4	1.8	515.77	720.4	21.8
YFIDFVAR	8.4	1.8	520.776	502.301	21.8
YFIDFVAR	8.4	1.8	520.776	617.328	21.8
YFIDFVAR	8.4	1.8	520.776	730.412	21.8
DYVSQFEGSALGK	8.4	1.8	700.838	279.098	23.9
DYVSQFEGSALGK	8.4	1.8	700.838	808.42	23.9
DYVSQFEGSALGK	8.4	1.8	700.838	1023.511	23.9
DYVSQFEGSALGK	8.4	1.8	704.845	279.098	23.9
DYVSQFEGSALGK	8.4	1.8	704.845	816.434	23.9
DYVSQFEGSALGK	8.4	1.8	704.845	1031.525	23.9
TYMLAFDVNDEK	8.4	1.8	723.334	265.118	23.4
TYMLAFDVNDEK	8.4	1.8	723.334	866.389	23.4
TYMLAFDVNDEK	8.4	1.8	723.334	937.426	23.4
TYMLAFDVNDEK	8.4	1.8	727.341	265.118	23.4
TYMLAFDVNDEK	8.4	1.8	727.341	874.403	23.4
TYMLAFDVNDEK	8.4	1.8	727.341	945.44	23.4
TLMFGSYLDDEK	8.5	1.8	709.829	215.139	24.2
TLMFGSYLDDEK	8.5	1.8	709.829	926.41	24.2
TLMFGSYLDDEK	8.5	1.8	709.829	1073.479	24.2
TLMFGSYLDDEK	8.5	1.8	713.836	215.139	24.2
TLMFGSYLDDEK	8.5	1.8	713.836	934.424	24.2
TLMFGSYLDDEK	8.5	1.8	713.836	1081.493	24.2
ITLPDFTGDLR	8.6	1.8	624.34	288.2	25.0
ITLPDFTGDLR	8.6	1.8	624.34	460.25	25.0
ITLPDFTGDLR	8.6	1.8	624.34	920.45	25.0
ITLPDFTGDLR	8.6	1.8	629.34	298.21	25.0
ITLPDFTGDLR	8.6	1.8	629.34	470.26	25.0
ITLPDFTGDLR	8.6	1.8	629.34	930.46	25.0
TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSK	8.8	1.8	937.465	234.145	31.0
TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSK	8.8	1.8	937.465	397.208	31.0
TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSK	8.8	1.8	937.465	836.417	31.0
TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSK	8.8	1.8	941.472	242.159	31.0
TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSK	8.8	1.8	941.472	405.222	31.0
TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSK	8.8	1.8	941.472	840.424	31.0

TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSR	8.8	1.8	951.468	850.42	31.4
TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSR	8.8	1.8	951.468	1178.548	31.4
TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSR	8.8	1.8	951.468	1293.575	31.4
TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSR	8.8	1.8	956.472	855.424	31.4
TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSR	8.8	1.8	956.472	1188.556	31.4
TTPPVLDSDGSFFLYSR	8.8	1.8	956.472	1303.583	31.4
WFYIASAFR	8.9	1.8	580.8	551.29	23.7
WFYIASAFR	8.9	1.8	580.8	664.38	23.7
WFYIASAFR	8.9	1.8	580.8	827.44	23.7
WFYIASAFR	8.9	1.8	585.8	561.3	23.7
WFYIASAFR	8.9	1.8	585.8	674.39	23.7
WFYIASAFR	8.9	1.8	585.8	837.45	23.7
LAEGFPLPLLK	8.9	1.8	599.37	470.33	24.3
LAEGFPLPLLK	8.9	1.8	599.37	680.47	24.3
LAEGFPLPLLK	8.9	1.8	599.37	884.56	24.3
LAEGFPLPLLK	8.9	1.8	603.37	478.35	24.3
LAEGFPLPLLK	8.9	1.8	603.37	688.49	24.3
LAEGFPLPLLK	8.9	1.8	603.37	892.58	24.3
FNKPFVFLMIEQNTK	8.9	1.8	619.33	497.28	17.5
FNKPFVFLMIEQNTK	8.9	1.8	619.33	863.43	17.5
FNKPFVFLMIEQNTK	8.9	1.8	619.33	993.56	17.5
FNKPFVFLMIEQNTK	8.9	1.8	622	497.28	17.5
FNKPFVFLMIEQNTK	8.9	1.8	622	871.44	17.5
FNKPFVFLMIEQNTK	8.9	1.8	622	993.56	17.5
SFFSFLGEAFDGAR	9.5	2	775.867	235.108	26.2
SFFSFLGEAFDGAR	9.5	2	775.867	822.374	26.2
SFFSFLGEAFDGAR	9.5	2	775.867	935.458	26.2
SFFSFLGEAFDGAR	9.5	2	780.871	235.108	26.2
SFFSFLGEAFDGAR	9.5	2	780.871	832.382	26.2
SFFSFLGEAFDGAR	9.5	2	780.871	945.466	26.2

Table 4: Vanquish NEO – TSQ Altis Plus method script

{Initial Time}	Instrument Setup
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.LoadingVolume Automatic
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.FastLoadingWanted Yes
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.KeepLoopInline No

Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DirectLoadingFlow	100.000 [µl/min]
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DirectLoadingMode	CombinedControl
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DirectLoadingPressure	1000.0 [bar]
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.TrapZebraWashCycles	4
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.TrapZebraWashWanted	No
Neo.PumpModule.Pump.FastColumnEquilibrationWanted	Yes
Neo.PumpModule.Pump.ColumnEquilibrationFactor	2
Neo.PumpModule.Pump.ColumnEquilibrationFlow	2.000 [µl/min]
Neo.PumpModule.Pump.ColumnEquilibrationMode	FlowControl
Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Equate	%B
Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%A.Equate	%A
Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%A_Solvent	H2O
Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B_Solvent	ACN
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.SolventWeakWpName	Solvent WWP
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.SolventStrongWpName	Solvent SWP
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.SolventWeakName	Solvent W
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.SolventStrongName	Solvent S
Neo.SamplerModule.TempCtrl	On
Neo.SamplerModule.Temperature.Nominal	7.0 [°C]
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.PunctureOffset	NoOffset
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.VialBottomDetection	On
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DispenseSpeed	5.000 [µl/s]
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DrawDelay	2.0 [s]
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DrawSpeed	0.200 [µl/s]
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.AirGapEnable	Off
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.OuterNeedleWashCycleTime	Default
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.InjectWashWeakTime	5.0 [s]
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.InjectWashWeakSpeed	80.0 [µl/s]
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.InjectWashStrongSpeed	80.0 [µl/s]
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.InjectWashStrongTime	3.0 [s]
Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.InjectWashMode	AfterDraw
Neo.ColumnCompartmentModule.ColumnChamber.TempCtrl	Off
Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.Diameter	150 [µm]
Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.Length	15.0 [cm]
Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.MaximumPressure	1000 [bar]
Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.MaximumFlow	100.0 [µl/min]
Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.MaximumTemperature	60.0 [°C]
Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.MaximumPressureChangeDown	1000 [bar/min]

	Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.MaximumPressureChangeUp	1000 [bar/min]
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.InjectionWorkflow	DirectInjection
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.FlowRegime	NanoCap
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.SystemSetup	VanquishNeo
0	Equilibration	Duration = 0.000 [min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	5.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
0	Inject Preparation	
	Wait	MSDevice.Ready And Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler. Ready And Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Ready And Neo.ColumnCompartmentModule. Ready And Neo.SystemControllerModule. Ready
0	Inject	
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.Inject	
0	Start Run	
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.Sampler_Pressure.AcqOn	
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Pump_Pressure.AcqOn	
0	Run	Duration = 15.000 [min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	5.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
5		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	15.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
10		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	50.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.StartColumnWash	
10.2		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	95.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5

13.2		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	95.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
13.4		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	5.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
15		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	5.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
15	Stop Run	
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.Sampler_Pressure.AcqOff	
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Pump_Pressure.AcqOff	
15	Post Run	Duration = 0.000 [min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.StartColumnEquilibration	
End		